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Mechanical Testing of Poly-Tetra-fluoro-ethylene (PTFE) filler compound

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Introduction: The PTFE (Poly-tetra-fluoro-ethylene) is a non-melt flow processable polymer. The raw material (resin) of PTFE is in the form of powder. This powder is then molded into the semi-finish or finish parts. PTFE is better known by the brand Teflon of Dupont. Dr. Roy J Plunkett from Dupont has invented PTFE accidentally during his experiment. Now the Teflon brand is owned by Chemours, which a spin-off business of Dupont.

Methods: The mechanical testing such as tensile strength, elongation, hardness and specific gravity has been carried out to check the mechanical properties of the PTFE. Similarly, the tests like dimensional stability, thermal instability index and deformation at 300° C temperature has been carried out to check the behavior of PTFE under high temperature conditions.

Results & Discussions: It shows that three compounds PTFE + 30% PEEK, PTFE + 5% Zirconia + 5% SiO₂ and RBC 006 have the lower values of deformation than virgin PTFE and other compounds. Therefore, they possess highest creep resistance as shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Creep test results at 3.45 MPa load with temperature of 300 °C for 24 hours.

Conclusions: It was observed that the increase in filler content reduces the tensile properties of PTFE and also molecular weight reduces with increased temperature. These are un-desirable properties for the study. But most of the applications demand for higher creep resistance at elevated temperature in compressive load. The result of creep test has clearly indicated that some of the fillers have very positive effect on increasing resistance to compressive creep. Mainly, 30% PEEK filled and RBC006 are the best compounds in such application up to 300 °C. Similar results were obtained for the dimensional stability test at 300 °C. By addition of PEEK, zirconia and silica has improved the dimensional stability at higher temperatures. Again the 30% PEEK filled and RBC006 were proved to be the best compounds.

Keywords: PTFE, Mechanical Properties, High Temperature, Creep Resistance, Testing and Analysis.

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